

2021 University Research Symposium Closing Keynote/Discussant

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- [Mladen Vouk](#), Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation
 - [View Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Sharon Joines](#), Associate Dean, College of Design
 - [View Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Kathie Dello](#), Director, The North Carolina State Climate Office
 - [View Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Micah Vandegrift](#), Open Knowledge Librarian, NC State University Libraries
 - [View Opening Remarks](#)
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Event Description:

To cap things off, Vice Chancellor Mladen Vouk, some of the week's presenters and moderators, and members of the 2021 symposium planning committee joined attendees for an open discussion and retrospective of the event, to identify key takeaways, suggest ways to build off the connections that were made and find other opportunities to capitalize on moving forward — in order to further strengthen the impacts of NC State's research and scholarship related to climate change and resilience.

You can [watch](#) the discussion in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Online Resources Shared:

- Concluding thoughts from Micah Vandegrift:
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fOI_TSRCE5R1jST-vbQpCGm5OR0vYJkOE518E_nyr8Q/edit#
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